

Compound: AgN_3
Materials Project ID: 571297

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	5.8273	Å
b	5.8273	Å
c	6.0257	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Ag₂Se
Materials Project ID: 568936

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.4975	Å
b	7.1133	Å
c	7.6707	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: AlPd₅I₂
 Materials Project ID: 27393

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.0783	Å
b	4.0783	Å
c	20.2662	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: AlPt
 Materials Project ID: 10904

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.9174	Å
b	4.9174	Å
c	4.9174	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Au
 Materials Project ID: 81

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.1713	Å
b	4.1713	Å
c	4.1713	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: BaAl₄
 Materials Project ID: 1903

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.5765	Å
b	4.5765	Å
c	11.3531	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: BaB₆
 Materials Project ID: 954

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.2801	Å
b	4.2801	Å
c	4.2801	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: BaSi₂
 Materials Project ID: 7655

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.0928	Å
b	4.0928	Å
c	5.3629	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: BaSn₂
 Materials Project ID: 567510

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.7650	Å
b	4.7650	Å
c	5.6084	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Be
 Materials Project ID: 87

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.2598	Å
b	2.2598	Å
c	3.5699	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Bi
 Materials Project ID: 23152

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.6096	Å
b	4.6096	Å
c	11.9755	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: BiTeI
Materials Project ID: 22965

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.4252	Å
b	4.4252	Å
c	7.3781	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Ca_2As
 Materials Project ID: 10106

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.5724	Å
b	4.5724	Å
c	15.8762	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CaAgAs
 Materials Project ID: 5615

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	7.2663	Å
b	7.2663	Å
c	4.3127	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CaAgBi
 Materials Project ID: 568664

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.9065	Å
b	4.9065	Å
c	7.8429	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CaAgP
Materials Project ID: 12277

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	7.0768	Å
b	7.0768	Å
c	4.2030	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CaB₆
 Materials Project ID: 865

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.1501	Å
b	4.1501	Å
c	4.1501	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CaBiAu
 Materials Project ID: 1018657

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.8612	Å
b	4.8612	Å
c	7.9224	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CaC₂
 Materials Project ID: 1077545

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.7480	Å
b	8.7387	Å
c	4.7766	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CaSi₂
 Materials Project ID: 8372

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.8878	Å
b	3.8878	Å
c	4.9460	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CaSnHg
 Materials Project ID: 1019104

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.9042	Å
b	4.9042	Å
c	7.8216	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CaTe
Materials Project ID: 10684

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.9261	Å
b	3.9261	Å
c	3.9261	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CaP₃
 Materials Project ID: 9122

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	5.6095	Å
b	5.6390	Å
c	5.6946	Å
α (alpha)	70.0761	°
β (beta)	79.6272	°
γ (gamma)	74.6843	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Co
 Materials Project ID: 54

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.5008	Å
b	2.5008	Å
c	4.0333	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CoGe
 Materials Project ID: 10692

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.6370	Å
b	4.6370	Å
c	4.6370	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CoSi
 Materials Project ID: 7577

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.4332	Å
b	4.4332	Å
c	4.4332	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: CoPtO₂
 Materials Project ID: 19210

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.8847	Å
b	2.8847	Å
c	18.2033	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Cu
 Materials Project ID: 30

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.6213	Å
b	3.6213	Å
c	3.6213	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Cu_3AsSe_4
 Materials Project ID: 675626

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	5.6212	Å
b	5.6212	Å
c	11.1400	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: GaPd
 Materials Project ID: 1078526

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.9634	Å
b	4.9634	Å
c	4.9634	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: GaPt
 Materials Project ID: 1025551

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.9729	Å
b	4.9729	Å
c	4.9729	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: GaGeTe
 Materials Project ID: 8211

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.1264	Å
b	4.1264	Å
c	36.5601	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: GeRh
 Materials Project ID: 20866

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.8620	Å
b	4.8620	Å
c	4.8620	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: HfB_2
 Materials Project ID: 1994

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.1487	Å
b	3.1487	Å
c	3.4799	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: HfCuP
 Materials Project ID: 569933

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.5872	Å
b	3.5872	Å
c	5.5801	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: InGaSe₂
 Materials Project ID: 1095059

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	8.1411	Å
b	8.1411	Å
c	6.4253	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: InTe
 Materials Project ID: 20320

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	8.6274	Å
b	8.6274	Å
c	7.2267	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Ir
 Materials Project ID: 101

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.8757	Å
b	3.8757	Å
c	3.8757	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: LaPIr
 Materials Project ID: 12919

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.1709	Å
b	4.1709	Å
c	14.3855	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: LaBiPt
 Materials Project ID: 1018136

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	6.9689	Å
b	6.9689	Å
c	6.9689	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: LiClO_2
 Materials Project ID: 31367

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.8313	Å
b	4.8313	Å
c	10.6884	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: LiHO
Materials Project ID: 23856

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.5914	Å
b	3.5914	Å
c	4.4105	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: LiYGe
 Materials Project ID: 14209

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	7.0924	Å
b	7.0924	Å
c	4.2591	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: LiYSi

Materials Project ID: 14208

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	7.0152	Å
b	7.0152	Å
c	4.2400	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Mo
 Materials Project ID: 129

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.1676	Å
b	3.1676	Å
c	3.1676	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: MoC
 Materials Project ID: 2305

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.9241	Å
b	2.9241	Å
c	2.8351	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: MoN
 Materials Project ID: 13036

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.8858	Å
b	2.8858	Å
c	2.8561	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: MoP
 Materials Project ID: 219

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.2446	Å
b	3.2446	Å
c	3.2005	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NbAs
 Materials Project ID: 2059

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.4847	Å
b	3.4847	Å
c	11.7615	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NbAs₂
 Materials Project ID: 7598

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	9.4518	Å
b	3.4178	Å
c	7.8850	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	119.3863	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NbInSe₂
 Materials Project ID: 20279

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.4646	Å
b	3.4646	Å
c	9.3914	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NbN
 Materials Project ID: 2634

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.9762	Å
b	2.9762	Å
c	2.8987	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NbP
 Materials Project ID: 9339

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.3564	Å
b	3.3564	Å
c	11.4365	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NbP₂
 Materials Project ID: 1077116

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	8.9129	Å
b	3.2925	Å
c	7.5664	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	118.9943	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NbS
 Materials Project ID: 2243

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.3186	Å
b	3.3186	Å
c	3.3243	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NbSe₄
 Materials Project ID: 1078815

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	5.9708	Å
b	5.9708	Å
c	6.5262	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NbSiAs
 Materials Project ID: 21907

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.5165	Å
b	3.5165	Å
c	7.9705	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Ni(BMo)₂
 Materials Project ID: 9999

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.1850	Å
b	4.5764	Å
c	7.1383	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NiS
 Materials Project ID: 1547

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	9.5644	Å
b	9.5644	Å
c	3.1260	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: NiSe
 Materials Project ID: 15651

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	10.0013	Å
b	10.0013	Å
c	3.3350	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Pd₂N
 Materials Project ID: 510087

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.9424	Å
b	4.8726	Å
c	5.4625	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Re
 Materials Project ID: 8

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.7811	Å
b	2.7811	Å
c	4.4971	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Ru
 Materials Project ID: 33

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.7329	Å
b	2.7329	Å
c	4.3139	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: ScGa₃
 Materials Project ID: 932

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.1216	Å
b	4.1216	Å
c	4.1216	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Se
 Materials Project ID: 14

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.5195	Å
b	4.5195	Å
c	5.0500	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: SiRh
 Materials Project ID: 1483

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.7295	Å
b	4.7295	Å
c	4.7295	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: ScCuGe
 Materials Project ID: 1078430

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	6.5606	Å
b	6.5606	Å
c	3.9977	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: SnH₄
 Materials Project ID: 1080725

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.9522	Å
b	3.9522	Å
c	6.4992	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: $\text{Sn}(\text{HgSe}_2)_2$
 Materials Project ID: 10955

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	5.9365	Å
b	5.9365	Å
c	11.9940	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Sr(CdSb)₂
 Materials Project ID: 7432

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.7972	Å
b	4.7972	Å
c	7.9056	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: $\text{Sr}_3(\text{AlGe})_2$
 Materials Project ID: 571216

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	12.7411	Å
b	4.2166	Å
c	8.9551	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	110.1782	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: SrAs₃
 Materials Project ID: 9907

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	9.7449	Å
b	7.7486	Å
c	5.9535	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	112.9053	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Sr₂Bi
 Materials Project ID: 29619

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	5.1526	Å
b	5.1526	Å
c	18.1556	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: SrGe₂
 Materials Project ID: 7390

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.1699	Å
b	4.1699	Å
c	5.1991	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: SrMnSb₂
 Materials Project ID: 1079721

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.4170	Å
b	4.4170	Å
c	11.7201	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: SrSi₂
 Materials Project ID: 1727

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.4377	Å
b	4.4377	Å
c	13.9661	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: SrSnHg
 Materials Project ID: 1019259

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	5.0060	Å
b	5.0060	Å
c	8.3087	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: TaAs
 Materials Project ID: 1936

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.4696	Å
b	3.4696	Å
c	11.7349	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: TaAs₂
 Materials Project ID: 12561

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	9.4399	Å
b	3.4259	Å
c	7.8478	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	119.7016	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: TaInS₂
 Materials Project ID: 22332

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.3249	Å
b	3.3249	Å
c	8.9364	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: TaN
 Materials Project ID: 1459

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.9540	Å
b	2.9540	Å
c	2.9015	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: TaP
 Materials Project ID: 1067587

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.3402	Å
b	3.3402	Å
c	11.4036	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: TaPbSe₂
 Materials Project ID: 567736

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.4835	Å
b	3.4835	Å
c	9.4755	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: TaSiAs
 Materials Project ID: 81

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.5206	Å
b	3.5206	Å
c	7.9142	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Te
 Materials Project ID: 19

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.5124	Å
b	4.5124	Å
c	5.9599	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Te_2Ir
 Materials Project ID: 2285

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.9878	Å
b	3.9878	Å
c	5.5433	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Te_2Mo
 Materials Project ID: 7459

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	6.3662	Å
b	3.4869	Å
c	15.5479	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	92.3879	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: Te_2W
 Materials Project ID:22693

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.4979	Å
b	6.3383	Å
c	15.4319	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: TiB_2
 Materials Project ID: 1145

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.0351	Å
b	3.0351	Å
c	3.2232	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: TiCu_2
 Materials Project ID: 1077023

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.5123	Å
b	7.9862	Å
c	4.4641	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: TiS
 Materials Project ID: 1018028

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.2739	Å
b	3.2739	Å
c	3.2191	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: WC
 Materials Project ID: 1894

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.9283	Å
b	2.9283	Å
c	2.8529	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: WN
 Materials Project ID: 991

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	2.8760	Å
b	2.8760	Å
c	2.9080	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: YAgPb
 Materials Project ID: 21505

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	7.5818	Å
b	7.5818	Å
c	4.5605	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: ZrB_2
 Materials Project ID: 1472

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.1805	Å
b	3.1805	Å
c	3.5455	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: ZrGePt
 Materials Project ID: 1095610

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	4.0158	Å
b	6.7301	Å
c	7.7560	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: ZrSiPt
 Materials Project ID: 972187

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.9323	Å
b	6.6654	Å
c	7.6233	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: ZrSiS
 Materials Project ID: 3938

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.6168	Å
b	3.6168	Å
c	8.6761	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	90.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: ZrSiSe
 Materials Project ID: 81

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.6168	Å
b	3.6168	Å
c	8.6761	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	$^\circ$
β (beta)	90.0000	$^\circ$
γ (gamma)	90.0000	$^\circ$

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

Compound: ZrTe
 Materials Project ID: 1539

Lattice (conventional cell):

Parameter	Value	Unit
a	3.7994	Å
b	3.7994	Å
c	3.8986	Å
α (alpha)	90.0000	°
β (beta)	90.0000	°
γ (gamma)	120.0000	°

Crystal structure (conventional cell):

Nanowire Transmission:

